

DESIGN, SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF 1,3 DIARYLTRIAZENE SUBSTITUTED SULPHACETAMIDE SODIUM DERIVATIVES AS ANTIOXIDANT

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ABSTRACT

In the past few decades, 1,3-diaryltriazenes had been synthesized and investigated their biological and pharmacological profiles. 1,3-diaryltriazenes compounds shows many activities like- anticancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-diabetic activities. The present study is focused on synthesis of novel series of 1,3-diaryltriazenes derivatives from diazonium salt of sulfacetamide sodium and substituted aniline via continuous stirring at 0 °C temp. for 3 hrs. A different color of compounds is obtained and the five novel compounds are confirmed by spectral analysis of NMR, MASS spectroscopy and FTIR. Antioxidant activity of the newly synthesized compound have been investigated by many radical scavenging assays. Compound SSR1 (4-[3-(4-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) and SSR5 (4-[3-(2-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have highest antioxidant potency presented (IC₅₀ value are 241.70 and 256.37 µg/mL respectively for DPPH method. In NO(nitric oxide) radical scavenging assay, compound SSR1(4-[3-(4-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) and SSR5(4-[3-(2-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have highest antioxidant value 75.80 % and 73.80 % respectively and reducing power antioxidant assay of the five compounds (SSR1-SSR5) were evaluated, compound SSR5 (4-[3-(2-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have highest antioxidant value.

Keywords: 1, 3-diaryltriazenes, Antioxidant, Sulpha drug, Free radicals, Scavenging methods, Oxidative stress.

INTRODUCTION

1.1.Triazene:

Triazene's are a class of nitrogen containing azo compound that hold three adjacent nitrogen atoms, (R-N=N-NH-R¹) and this three-nitrogen atom responsible for the physiochemical and biological properties of the molecule.^[1-2] Triazenyl group is the essential active moiety of triazene compounds^[3-4] and they have broad spectrum of biological activities such as lipid lowering, antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antibacterial, insecticidal and analgesic agents.^[5-10]

Triazene can be used as biological and chemical reagents in industry and involved in organic synthesis. Metallic complexes of triazene are show anti-tumor and anticancer activity. Some triazene substituted compounds such as Dacarbazine (DTIC), Temozolomide (TMZ), Mitozolomide (INN) which are used in clinical practice. These compounds have been used to

developed anticancer drug due to their low toxicity and good pharmacokinetic properties. [11-15]

Dacarbazine (DTIC)

Temozolomide (TMZ)

Mitozolomide (INN)

Figure 1. Triazene substituted compounds

1,3-Di aryltriazenes substituted sulfonamide having inhibition effect on different metabolic enzymes which are responsible for many diseases. This type of triazene compound has been studied as potent metabolic enzyme inhibitors. [16]

1.2. Antioxidant:

Antioxidant are substance that able to either delay or prevent or slow the oxidation of the substrate by reacting and eliminating oxidizing free radicals, and reduced oxidative stress, DNA mutation and other parameters of cell damage. [17-19] It may be used as food additives, which prevent foods from oxidation and increase their self-life by lipid per-oxidation retardation process. They are also involved in industrial products to reduce or prevent the oxidative degradation of many products like plastics, rubbers and adhesive and widely used to prevent rancidity of lipsticks and moisturizers. [20-21]

1.2.1. Oxidative stress:

The imbalance between the generations of reactive species (ROS- reactive oxygen specie and RNS- reactive nitrogen species) and ability to neutralize free radical into the living organism are known as Oxidative Stress. Reactive species are known as free radicals which are release in living organism during various chemical reaction on the metabolism procedure. It was reported that over 100 diseases are correlated with oxidative stress. It is involved in immune response to viral respiratory infections. [22-24]

Image-1. Cell damage due to oxidative stress.

Table: 1. Oxidative stress related diseases.

S.no.	Chronic conditions (Disease)
1	Cancer
2	Parkinson's diseases
3	Diabetes
4	High blood pressure
5	Atherosclerosis
6	Stoke
7	Asthma
8	Male infertility
9	Chronic fatigue syndrome
10	Inflammatory disorder
11	Alzheimer's disease

1.2.1.1. Free radicals:

The ions, atoms, or molecules which have unpaired electron (single electron) are known as free radicals. They are highly reactive and unstable due to this, free radical quickly react with other molecules in to the living organism and make some damage which are responsible for many kinds of disease. Free radicals are including superoxide [$O_2^{\cdot-}$], peroxy [$ROO\cdot$], alkoxy [$RO\cdot$], hydroxyl [$OH\cdot$] and nitric oxide [$NO\cdot$] radicals which responsible for many chronic health problems such as, [Neurodegenerative conditions, (Parkinson, Huntington's disease and Alzheimer), inflammation, cardiovascular disease and cancer]. Reactive oxygen species mainly found in the electron transport chain [ETC] at the mitochondrial inner membrane where energy is generated in the form of ATP. [25-28] The production of ROS is dependent on the metabolic pathway, environmental pollution, UV irradiation and others. [29-31]

1.2.2. Antioxidant reactivity:

Antioxidant is the compounds that protect body from toxic effect of free radicals. If free radical is not removing from the body, they cause a chain reaction which is responsible for oxidative stress. The protective mechanism of antioxidant is by decomposing peroxidase, scavenging free radicals or binding with p-oxidant metal ion. The mechanism of antioxidant is dependent on the redox reactions in which unpaired of electron is transfer from one

compound (molecule) to the other compound and the loss of electrons are used to maintain oxidation states on the both sides. [32]

Antioxidants acts at different levels and it classify into three categories on the basis of mechanism of action. [33]

1- Primary antioxidants-

This antioxidant responsible to preventing the initiation of chain reaction by suppressing the formation of free radical. (Example- Catalase, Selenoprotein, ferritin, Transferrin, Lactoferrin, Glutathione peroxidase, Carotenoid etc.)

Figure 2. Prevention of chain reaction initiation by Glutathione peroxidase.

2- Secondary antioxidants-

Those antioxidants which are involved by interrupting chain sequence of scavenging free radicals generated chain reaction and braking chain propagation reaction.

3- Tertiary antioxidants-

They act by removing peroxidase, thereby preventing further generation of reactive species and repair to oxidized molecules. (Example- Proteolytic enzyme, Enzyme of DNA)

Figure 3. Mechanism action of antioxidant.

On the basis of above information, the present work is aimed to synthesize novel 1,3-diaryl triazene substituted sulfonamides sodium derivatives (SSR1-SSR5) and evaluate their antioxidant activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material and methods:

All the chemicals and solvents, purchased from Merck (India), Spectrochem (India), Sigma-Aldrich (India), CDH (India) and S.D. Fine were used without further purification. Thin layer chromatographic analysis of compounds was performed on silica gel G coated glass plates. The adsorbent silica gel G was coated to a thickness of about 0.25 mm on previously cleaned TLC plates of 20x5 cm using conventional spreader. The plates were placed in hot air oven at 105°C for 30 min. The solutions of compounds were applied as a spot on the activated plate about 2 cm above from the lower edge. The mobile phases were selected according to the polarity of compounds. Melting points were determined by using open capillary melting point apparatus and are reported uncorrected. Compounds were placed in one end of the sealed capillary and placed in the caves made for the capillary. Thermometer was placed in the cave. The temperature at which compound starts melting and the temperature at which it completely melts was recorded as a melting point range. Infra-red spectra of synthesized compounds were recorded in Perkin Elmer – Spectrum RX- IFTIR spectrometer. The proton-nuclear-magnetic resonance spectra of synthesized compound were record on Bruker 500MHz High Resolution NMR spectrometer by TMS an internal level. DMSO was used as solvent to record 1H NMR spectra. Chemical shifts were reported in ppm (δ) and signals were represented as singlet (s), doublet (d) and multiplet (m). and Mass -to- charge ratio (m/z) of the molecules of synthesized compound (SSR1-SSR5) was identified by the MICROMASS Q-TOF micro-Mass spectrometer.

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds [SSR1-SSR5]:

First step, a solution of standard compound (Sulphacetamide sodium) in 1.5 ml of concentrated HCl and 10 ml of cooled water at 0-5°C was prepared with continuous stirring in a conical flask. In another beaker, 7mmol of sodium nitrite was dissolved in 5 ml water and added drop wise in conical flask for about 20-25 minutes with stirring on the magnetic stirrer until mixed well. Geoffrey D. Picard et al, the conversion of iodine starch paper color white to blue indicated the formation of diazonium salt. [34]

Second step, a solution of substituted aniline (R1-R5) was prepared by dissolved 5mmol of substituted aniline with 5 ml of methanol in a beaker. this solution was added to diazonium salt solution with continuous stirring for 3 hours and maintain the temperature of reaction mixture between 0-5°C. The pH of reaction mixture was adjusted around 5-7 by adding sodium acetate buffer and monitored the reaction through TLC. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours at room temperature in dark place. The colorful mass was obtained and then was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallized from ethanol. The anilines which are used in the synthesis of sulfa drug based 1,3-diaryltriazenes derivatives are as follows: 4-methyl aniline (1), 4-amino acetophenone (2), 4-fluoro aniline (3), 4- nitro aniline (4) and 2- methyl aniline (5). The obtained colorful products (SSR1-SSR5) were characterized by FT-IR, ¹HNMR, MASS spectroscopy and melting points.

Scheme: 1.

Synthesize compound is- (SSR1-SSR5)

Chemicals and conditions:

- (i) H₂O, con. HCL, NaNO₂, 0-5°C, ½ hr;
 (ii) substituted aromatic anilines (R1-R5),
 CH₃-OH, H₂O, saturated sodium acetate 0-5°C, stirring 3hr, r.m. overnight.

S.no.	Compounds	R	Molecular formula	Calculated Molecular Weight
1.	SSR1		C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₄ NaO ₃ S	354.36
2.	SSR2		C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ NaO ₄ S	382.36
3.	SSR3		C ₁₄ H ₁₂ FN ₄ NaO ₃ S	358.32
4.	SSR4		C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₅ NaO ₅ S	385.33
5.	SSR5		C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₄ NaO ₃ S	354.36

Table: 2. Physical data of all compounds substituted Aniline.

Characterization of the synthesized compounds (SSR1-SSR5)-

Compound-1: 4-[3-(4-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium (SSR1)

Physical parameters:

Percentage yield: 60%

Color: Carrot color

Melting Point: 159-161°C

R_f value: 0.65

Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₅N₄NaO₃S

Characterization: FT-IR: NH(3238cm⁻¹), N=N(1598cm⁻¹), S=O(1150cm⁻¹), C-N(1500cm⁻¹), C=O(1687cm⁻¹), CH₃(1259cm⁻¹); ¹H-NMR(DMSO-d₆ -500MHz), δ7.62-8.15(m,8H,Ar-H), 2.51-2.58(d, 3H,-CH₃), 1.94(s, 3H,-CO-CH₃), 13.15(s,1H, NH). MS(m/z):354.07. M⁺.

Compound-2: 4-[3-(4-acetyl-phenyl) -triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium (SSR2)

Physical parameters:

Percentage yield: 57%

Color: Yellow color

Melting Point: 178-280°C

R_f value: 0.68

Molecular formula: C₁₆H₁₅N₄NaO₄S

Characterization: FT-IR: NH(3250-3054cm⁻¹), N=N(1509cm⁻¹), S=O(1148cm⁻¹), C-N(1442 cm⁻¹), C=O(1604cm⁻¹), CH₃(1335cm⁻¹); ¹H-NMR (DMSO-d₆ -500MHz), δ7.62-8.15 (m,8H,Ar-H), 2.51-2.58(d,3H, -CH₃), 1.94(s,3H,-CO-CH₃), 12.15(s,1H,NH). MS(m/z):354.07. M⁺.

Compound-3: 4-[3-(4-fluoro phenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium (SSR3)

Physical parameters:

Percentage yield: 57%

Color: Grey color

Melting Point: 169-172°C

R_f value: 0.75

Molecular formula: C₁₄H₁₂FN₄NaO₃S

Characterization: FT-IR: NH(3272-3092 cm⁻¹), N=N(1599cm⁻¹), S=O(1155cm⁻¹), C-N(1456 cm⁻¹), C=O(1687cm⁻¹), CH₃(1306cm⁻¹); ¹H-NMR(DMSOd₆ -500 MHz), δ7.93-8.80 (m, 8H, Ar-H), 1.94 (s, 3H, -CO-CH₃), 10.04(s, 1H, NH). MS(m/z):358.09. M⁺.

Compound-4: 4-[3-(4-nitrophenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium(SSR4)

Physical parameters:

Percentage yield: 49%

Color: Turmeric color

Melting Point: 165-167 °C

R_f value: 0.64

Molecular formula: C₁₄H₁₂N₅NaO₅S

Characterization: FT-IR:NH (3243-3053cm⁻¹), N=N(1599cm⁻¹), S=O(1154cm⁻¹), C-N(1441 cm⁻¹), C=O(1644 cm⁻¹), CH₃(1266 cm⁻¹); ¹H-NMR (DMSOd₆ -500MHz), δ6.93-7.54 (m, 8H, Ar-H), 2.51-2.58(d, 3H, -CO-CH₃), 13.15 (s, 1H, NH). MS(m/z):385.08. M⁺.

Compound-5: 4-[3-(2-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium (SSR5)

Physical parameters:

Percentage yield: 51%

Color: Reddish color

Melting Point: 167-69°C

R_f value: 0.65

Molecular formula: C₁₅H₁₅N₄NaO₃S

Characterization: FT-IR: NH(3238 cm⁻¹), N=N(1598cm⁻¹), S=O (1150cm⁻¹), C-N(1452cm⁻¹), C=O(1635cm⁻¹), CH₃ (1259cm⁻¹); ¹H-NMR(DMSO d₆ -500 MHz), δ7.61-8.14 (m,8H,Ar-H), 1.94 (d,3H, -CO-CH₃), 2.51-2.58(d, 3H,-CH₃), 13.15(s,1H,NH). MS(m/z):354.07. M⁺.

PHARMACOLOGICAL EVALUATION:

Antioxidant methods:

The measurement of free radical scavenging activity of sulfa drug based triazene is continually related free radical scavenging method to search the in-vitro activity. Antioxidant activity of newly synthesized 1,3-diaryl triazene sulfacetamide sodium derivatives were evaluated by various method.

Nitric oxide scavenging assay. ^[35]

Reducing power antioxidant assay, ^[36]

DPPH radical scavenging method, ^[37]

Standard compound was also analyses for their antioxidant properties and a comparative study was done with the novel synthesized compounds.

Nitric oxide scavenging assay:

Ebrahimzadeh et al. procedure was adopted to calculate the scavenging capacity of the synthesized compounds against nitric oxide radical. The procedure was carried out with nitroprusside which responsible for the formation of nitric oxide. Nitric oxide is converted into nitrite ion when it's come in the contact of oxygen. Griess reagent are involved in the reaction and formed a colored complex with nitrite ion. The antioxidant compounds reduced the formation of nitrite ion and the color of final mixture in depend on the potency of antioxidant. So, if the compound has more antioxidant activity, then the colorless solution obtained. The absorbance of colored mixture was readied at 546nm against the blank.

The compounds were primarily subjected for evaluating their antioxidant activity by nitric oxide scavenging assay. The result are shown in the table-8. synthesized compound SSR1 (75.8%), SSR2 (64.8%), SSR3 (20.2%), SSR4 (39.4%) and SSR5 (73.2%) have been represented the highest antioxidant values at 10 ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) concentration of sample with respect to standard ascorbic acid. compound SSR1 (4-[3-(4-methylphenyl) -triaz-1-en-1-yl] -N-sulfanyl acetamide sodium) and SSR5 (4-[3-(2-methylphenyl) -triaz-1-en-1-yl] -N-sulfanyl acetamide sodium) have highest antioxidant value 75.80 % and 73.80 % respectively.

Reducing power antioxidant assay:

Reducing powers antioxidant assays is a developed assay for measure antioxidant capacity of samples, which is based on conversion of the ferric ion to ferrous ion by antioxidant molecules forming the colored complex. This procedure was adopted to calculate the scavenging capacity of synthesized compounds, in which different concentration (10, 25, 50 & 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of synthesized compounds and standard was prepared with methanol. For the further procedure phosphate buffer (2.5ml, 0.2M, pH-6.6) and potassium ferricyanide (2.5ml, 1% solution) added to each test tube including the blank test tube. Incubated the all-test tube mixture at 50 °C temperature for 25min. and after 25min. Trichloroacetic acid (2.5 mL, 10%) added. Then centrifuge mixture at 2500rpm for 10min and separated out upper layer of mixture. Then dissolved the supernatant with distilled water (2.5mL) and ferric chloride (0.5mL) 0.1% solution and read absorbance at 700nm and to calculate the scavenging activity (%) using following equation.

$$\text{Scavenging effect (\%)} = \left[\frac{\text{Abs}_{\text{control}} - \text{Abs}_{\text{sample}}}{\text{Abs}_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100$$

*Abs_{control} - Absorbance of control, Abs_{sample} - Absorbance of sample.

The reducing power antioxidant assay was used to determine the reducing power of compounds (SSR1-SSR5) to clarify the relationship between the antioxidant effect and the reducing power (Table-9). It was found that compound SSR1 (4-[3-(4-methylphenyl) -triaz-1-en-1-yl] -N- sulfanyl acetamide sodium) showed relatively low antioxidant power as compared to other compounds whereas compound SSR5 (4-[3-(2-methylphenyl) -triaz-1-en-1-yl] -N- sulfanyl acetamide sodium) shown relatively high antioxidant power 0.472 optical density value.

DPPH free radical scavenging method:

Procedure was adopted to calculate the scavenging potency of the synthesized compounds against DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) free radical reagent. In this method, the reduction of the purple DPPH free radical is occurring due to the accepting electron or radical hydrogen from antioxidant (SSR1-H).

range 114.89 ± 2.50 to 813.65 ± 1.18 and $>1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for DPPH and 25.31 ± 0.21 to 610.34 ± 3.07 and $>1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for ABTS. [39] In the present study, A series of structurally diverse 1,3-diaryltriene substituted sulfonamide sodium derivatives were synthesized according to modified synthetic route as presented in scheme-1. The final compound confirmed by FTIR, ¹HNMR and MASS spectroscopy.

BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION:

Antioxidant activity:

All the five synthesized compounds (SSR1-SSR5) were screened for their possible in vitro antioxidant activity through different in vitro modules such as 1,1-Diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl radical (DPPH), nitric oxide (NO) radical scavenging and ferric ion reducing antioxidant power assay. Observed results indicated that, few of the tested compounds are significant in their antioxidant properties.

Absorbance of synthesized compounds at various concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in nitric oxide radical scavenging model.

Absorbance of SSR1 compound at concentration in nitric oxide radical scavenging model	
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.121 ± 0.004
25	0.099 ± 0.006
50	0.135 ± 0.003
100	0.151 ± 0.001

Table: 3. Absorbance of SSR1

Absorbance of SSR2 compound at concentration in nitric oxide radical scavenging model	
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.176 ± 0.007
25	0.325 ± 0.004
50	0.406 ± 0.026
100	0.483 ± 0.023

Table: 4. Absorbance of SSR2

Absorbance of SSR3 compound at concentration in nitric oxide radical scavenging model	
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.399 \pm 0.002
25	0.426 \pm 0.006
50	0.495 \pm 0.005
100	1.229 \pm 0.001

Table: 5. Absorbance of SSR3

Absorbance of SSR4 compound at concentration in nitric oxide radical scavenging model	
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.303 \pm 0.010
25	0.610 \pm 0.011
50	1.165 \pm 0.024
100	2.000 \pm 0.173

Table: 6. Absorbance of SSR4

Absorbance of SSR5 compound at concentration in nitric oxide radical scavenging model	
Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
10	0.131 \pm 0.057
25	0.127 \pm 0.036
50	0.250 \pm 0.083
100	0.301 \pm 0.019

Table: 7. Absorbance of SSR5

Percentage inhibition of the synthesized compounds at various concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in nitric oxide radical scavenging model.

Figure 4. Percentage inhibition of SSR1

Figure 5. Percentage inhibition of SSR2

Figure 6. Percentage inhibition of SSR3

Figure 7. Percentage inhibition of SSR4

Figure 8. Percentage inhibition of SSR5

Table 8: Antioxidant activity percentage comparison study with standard and synthesized compounds in Nitric oxide (NO) method

S.no.	Compound	Standard % (Ascorbic acid)	Concentration (µg/ml)			
			10	25	50	100
1	SSR1	100	75.8	80.2	73	69.8
2	SSR2	100	64.8	35	18.8	3.4
3	SSR3	100	20.2	14.8	1	-145.8
4	SSR4	100	39.4	-22	-133	-300
5	SSR5	100	73.8	74.6	50	39.8

Table: 9. Reducing power of compounds (SSR1-SSR5).

*Data expressed the means of three replicates (OD-optical density)

Compound (OD)	Concentration			
	10	25	50	100
SSR1	0.288	0.317	0.367	0.431
SSR2	0.295	0.323	0.385	0.421
SSR3	0.302	0.379	0.401	0.395
SSR4	0.332	0.383	0.425	0.428
SSR5	0.301	0.344	0.416	0.472
Control	0.042	0.042	0.042	0.042

Ferric reducing power determination of standard ascorbic acid and synthesized compounds (SSR1-SSR5):

Figure 9. Ferric reducing power determination of standard ascorbic acid

Figure 10. Ferric reducing power determination of SSR1

Figure 11. Ferric reducing power determination of SSR2

Figure 12. Ferric reducing power determination of SSR3

Figure 13. Ferric reducing power determination of SSR4

Figure 14. Ferric reducing power determination of SSR5

Table: 10. The in-vitro antioxidant activity of compounds (SSR1-SSR5) in DPPH method

S.no.	Compound	Concentration (µg/ml)				
		10	25	50	100	IC50
1	SSR1	6.2	17.65	23.95	30.50	241.7±15.50
2	SSR2	11.13	20.85	29.64	44.51	212.5±3.27
3	SSR3	43.08	58.18	57.34	61.68	131.9±12.78
4	SSR4	22.57	27.28	35.86	42.75	180.5±7.31
5	SSR5	11.28	20.61	25.91	39.11	256.37±2.27
6	Ascorbic acid	27.49	41.07	49.15	67.30	23.11±2.05

*Scavenging activity values were the means of three replicates

Table: 11. Antioxidant activity percentage comparison study with standard and synthesized compounds in DPPH method

S.no.	Compound	Standard % (Ascorbic acid)	Concentration (µg/ml)			
			10	25	50	100
1	SSR1	100	23.6	25	28.2	35.6

2	SSR2	100	20.2	7.8	5	17
3	SSR3	100	28	30	23	34
4	SSR4	100	8	5.6	7.4	18
5	SSR5	100	36.2	33	29.6	39.6

CONCLUSION

In the present research work, five newly 1, 3-diaryltriazene compounds were synthesized by substituted aromatic aniline with diazonium salt of Sulphacetamide sodium and characterized by spectral analytical techniques. On basis of results, all five 1,3-diaryltriazene compounds were shown antioxidant activity which is investigated by DPPH free radical scavenging assay, reducing power antioxidant assay and nitric oxide (NO) radical scavenging assays. Compound SSR1(4-[3-(4-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) and SSR5(4-[3-(2-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have highest antioxidant activity presented IC₅₀ value 241.70µg/mL and 256.37µg/mL respectively and compound SSR3 and compound SSR4 (4-[3-(4-nitrophenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have lowest antioxidant activity presented IC₅₀ value 131.90µg/mL and 180.50µg/mL respectively for DPPH method. In nitric oxide (NO) radical scavenging assay, compound SSR1(4-[3-(4-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) and SSR5(4-[3-(2-methylphenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have highest antioxidant value 75.80 % and 73.80 % respectively and reducing power antioxidant assay of the five compounds (SSR1-SSR5) were evaluated, compound SSR5(4-[3-(2-methyl phenyl) -triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have highest and compound SSR3(4-[3-(4-fluoro phenyl)-triaz-1-en-1-yl]-N-sulfanilyl acetamide sodium) have lowest antioxidant value. If the compounds further explored, they can be more potent for multi-target or disease.

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